

Synthesis, characterization, DFT studies, and immobilization of cobalt(II) complex with *N,N,N'*-tris(2-pyrimidinyl)dimethylethylamine on modified iron oxide as oxidation catalyst

Masoomeh Sharbatdaran^a, Faezeh Farzaneh^{b,*}, Majid Mojtahedzadeh Larijani^c, Alireza Salimi^d, Mina Ghiasi^d, Mehdi Ghandi^e

^a Physics and Accelerators School, Nuclear Sciences and Technology Research Institute, Karaj, Iran

^b Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics and Chemistry, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

^c Radiation Application Research School, Nuclear Sciences and Technology Research Institute, Tehran, Iran

^d Department of Chemistry, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Mashhad, Iran

^e School of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 26 January 2016

Accepted 10 May 2016

Available online 17 May 2016

Keywords:

Cobalt complex
N,N,N'-tris(2-pyrimidinyl)
dimethylethylamine
Magnetic nanoparticles
Oxidation
Alkenes

ABSTRACT

[Co₃(PDMT)Cl₆] complex, in which PDMT is *N,N,N'*-tris(2-pyrimidinyl)dimethylethylamine was prepared in cyclohexanol under hydrothermal condition. At first, the crystal structure of PDMT was solved based on the Rietveld method by using laboratory X-ray powder diffraction data. The molecular geometry of the ligand and complex were optimized by B3LYP method. In order to heterogenize the prepared complex, it was immobilized on the modified Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with (3-aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane (APTMS). The prepared compound designated as Fe₃O₄@SiO₂-2@APTMS@[Co₃(PDMT)Cl₆] was found to successfully catalyze the epoxidation of cyclooctene, styrene, cyclohexene, *trans*-stilbene as well as oxidation of fluorene, diphenylmethane, ethylbenzene, adamantane, cyclohexane, cyclooctane and norbornene with TBHP as oxidant with 25–100% conversions and 18–100% selectivities. Ligand, complex and Fe₃O₄@SiO₂-2@APTMS@[Co₃(PDMT)Cl₆] were characterized by FT-IR, TEM, XRD, Mass, UV–Vis, DSC-TGA, NMR, GC and GC-Mass techniques.

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1. Introduction

An intense research focus remains on the synthesis and characterization of cobalt complex due to their huge impact on biological applications especially using as catalyst in the development of organic reactions [1–8]. Recently, several cobalt complexes have been synthesized and structurally determined with some multifunctional ligands such as imidazole-based dicarboxylic ligands [9], carboxylate and phthalate anions [10–12], tetra-dentate Schiff base ligands [13], *n*-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) and poly-nitrogen-donor ligands [14,15]. The resulting complexes were used in various fields since utilization of the cobalt transition metal in organic transformations has attracted increasing interest especially due to its lower cost when compared with its higher homologues [16].

During the last years, significant efforts were dedicated to the heterogenization of homogeneous catalysis systems in order to combine the advantages of heterogeneous and homogeneous

catalysts such as easier product/catalyst separation and higher selectivity [17–26]. Among the studied various supporting materials, magnetic nanoparticles and nanoassemblies with uniform size distribution are currently of emerging interest because of their extensive applications in memory storage devices, catalysis, sensors, MRI, magnetically controlled drug delivery and hyperthermia treatment of tumor cells [27–30]. Magnetic particles are also one of the most popular materials with increasingly use in immobilizing proteins, enzymes, and other bioactive agents in analytical biochemistry, medicine, and biotechnology [29,31,32]. Iron oxides and other iron-containing nanoparticles have widely been studied among the magnetic nanomaterials.

The immobilization of the catalytically active species on the surface of modified magnetic particles is a suitable method because of the easy catalyst separation by applying an external magnetic field [31,33,34]. Several organic reactions such as decarboxylative coupling [35], olefin epoxidation [36], hydrogenation and asymmetric hydrogenation [37] reactions have been carried out using nanomagnetic particles as support [38–41].

Catalytic oxidation is an important technology that finds applications in all kinds of chemical industries. Epoxidation of cyclic

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +98 21 88258977; fax: +98 21 +98 21 88041344.
E-mail addresses: faezeh_farzaneh@yahoo.com, Farzaneh@alzahra.ac.ir (F. Farzaneh).

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